

The use of a benchmark periodic metamaterial to inform numerical modelling and additive manufacturing approaches.

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Abstract

The development of metamaterial modelling tools requires agreed benchmark designs which are suitable for manufacture and acoustic testing. A proposed design for a benchmark metamaterial consists of a periodic structure of cubes with a spherical internal cavity connected through cylindrical openings on each face of the cube. This design is highly amenable to both numerical modelling and manufacture through additive techniques. This work will report on the design, manufacture, modelling and validation of this benchmark metamaterial. The influence of manufacturing deviations on the predicted acoustic behaviour will be quantitatively assessed through acoustic testing. Furthermore, deliberate deviations from the basic design will be introduced during the manufacture to allow a systematic assessment of the impact of the manufacturing tolerances on the targeted meta-behaviour. Thereby this work will produce initial guidance on the impact of additive manufacturing approaches on the performance of acoustic metamaterials.

1 Introduction

The European COST action DENORMS (Designs for Noise Reducing Materials and Structures) has the stated goal of providing a framework for efficient information exchange, avoiding duplication of research efforts and channelling the work of groups involved towards the common goal of designing multifunctional, light and compact noise reducing treatments. As part of this effort there is a need for benchmark designs and materials which can be used to cross check and validate new numerical approaches as well as experimental measurements and manufacturing technologies. The group proposed a design for a benchmark periodic metamaterial which was amenable to numerical modelling, manufacture and experimental testing. This work reports on initial results for the proposed design where the entire process of simulation, manufacture, experimental testing and validation was attempted.

The recent surge in metamaterial research has been facilitated by a number of advances in enabling technologies. Advances in numerical modelling and processing power have enabled the simulation of meta-behaviours under realistic conditions. This has led to proposals for effective designs however, until recently, these were often unrealisable. Research into advanced additive manufacturing technologies has opened the door to complex geometries that are unsuited to traditional manufacturing techniques. At present there are a number of additive manufacturing technologies available and these include:

- Stereolithography
- Jetting systems
- Direct Light Processing
- Laser Metal Deposition

- Electron Beam Melting
- Lithography-based Ceramic Manufacturing
- Selective laser melting/sintering
- Fused Deposition Modelling

The various technologies provide different capabilities in terms of resolution and build volumes. These limit the scale and quantity of metamaterial that can be produced. The design and manufacturing processes from conception through to realization of a metamaterial is also of vital importance as is it currently unknown to what extent manufacturing tolerances or defects will impact the targeted meta-behaviour. Therefore the correct selection of manufacturing process and inspection of the produced material are topics which require research.

A survey of the state of the art in terms of additive manufacturing technologies reveals the capabilities currently available to metamaterial researchers. The key capabilities of build volume and minimum feature size have been graphed in figure 1. The graph shows a clear relationship between the build volume and minimum feature size and shows the overlap in the capabilities of the various technologies considered. As a general rule an increase in build volume is matched by a corresponding increase in the minimum feature size which can be achieved. There were three printing technologies used for this research which extend from low cost desktop printers to the state of the art machines. One of the most widely used low cost (approx. €3k) desktop printers is the Ultimaker series highlighted by a red ∇ on the plot. The Formlabs Form 2 is a relatively low cost desktop printer (approx. €5k) highly suited to laboratory research of metamaterials as many prototype designs can be produced quickly and cost effectively and is highlighted with a red + on the plot. The 3D Systems Prox DMP 200, highlighted by the red \triangleright symbol, can print in titanium, cobalt chrome, aluminium and stainless steel. This is a state of the art machine (approx. €450k) and in this work was used to manufacture in cobalt chrome at a cost of €200 per kilo of powder.

2 Design

The DENORMS benchmark design consists of a periodic structure of cubes with spherical internal cavities connected through cylindrical openings on each face of the cube. This design, while basic, has a number of features which can be varied to alter the acoustic performance of the periodic cellular material. It is also amenable to manufacture at different scales and with the parameters of sphere and cylinder diameter easily varied within a cell of a given size.

In this work a single 5mm cubed cell size was used with fixed interior spherical cavities of radius 2.25mm with interconnecting cylinders of radius 1mm from all faces of the cell. These parameters were chosen in the first instance to allow for a successful manufacture of the structure. Figures 2 and 3 show the dimension and design design of the periodic cell.

While the DENORMS cell does not correspond closely to many of the wide range of metamaterial designs currently published in literature the lessons learned for the manufacture, simulation and testing are still widely applicable to other materials. For example, recent papers on: optimal sound absorber design [1], ultra thin metasurfaces [2] and space coiling metamaterials [3, 4, 5] have all utilised periodic structures realised through additive manufacturing.

3 Manufacture

Most low cost commercial 3D printers make use of fused filament fabrication which is a 3D printing process that uses a continuous filament of a thermoplastic material, for example the Ultimaker desktop printers.

Figure 1: Build volume and minimum feature size for commercial additive manufacturing systems

Figure 2: DENORMS benchmark design

Figure 3: DENORMS benchmark design- rotation of individual cell from zero to twenty five degrees

The resolution of these machines is potentially insufficient to accurately manufacture the spherical internal cavities and circular openings of the connecting cylinders which are included in this material's design. Additionally these "fuzzy" internal surfaces may influence the achieved acoustic performance, potentially leading to an enhanced broadband performance [4] due to additional losses caused by the spurs. It is not possible to quantify the influence of these manufacturing defects on the achieved acoustic performance of the material therefore they may be unsuitable for a benchmark validation material. The Formlabs Form 2 printer which is based on stereolithography technology can achieve a resolution which is, conservatively, four times smaller than Ultimaker technology while still being a low cost desktop printer. It is hoped that more accurate manufacturing will lead to greater agreement with the numerical simulations of the acoustic behaviour. Finally the 3D Systems Prox DMP 200, based on selective laser melting/sintering, can achieve the smoothest surfaces with the best resolution and will be the closest to the ideal benchmark material sample. Manufacture with these three different technologies essentially introduces defects into the design which are inherent to the technology chosen.

There are however significant disadvantages to all of these technologies when considering a periodic cellular design. For the stereolithography based printers the entrainment of the resin material inside the cells leads to blockages which are more difficult to remove deeper in the material. This limits the number of layers of cells which can be manufactured in a single piece. This problem is not encountered in fused filament fabrication as there is no excess material to be entrained inside the cells. In this work attempts were made to remove the entrained resin material through compressed air cleaning, ultrasonic baths and manual evacuation. A decision was made to print the cells in high resolution single and dual layers which could be combined for testing. This introduces a new complication in that it is possible to have air gaps between layers of the cells, the effect of which may be very significant on the acoustic performance. A move to selective laser melting/sintering in metals avoids all of the above issues, however this technology can no longer be considered low cost. The additive manufacturing process is outlined in figure 4.

Stage one occurs in the Computer Aided Design Laboratory where the component CAD files are analysed and prepared for the additive manufacturing process. The following software packages are used at TCD for this purpose:

- CAD Software: SolidWorks, Creo
- Finite Element Analysis: Ansys Workbench
- 3D Printing Software: Materialise, 3D Builder, PreForm

The second stage is the additive manufacturing process where the appropriate technology is chosen based on consideration such as:

- Material: Polymer, ceramic, titanium, aluminium, cobalt chrome, stainless steel
- Build volume
- Resolution
- Manufacturing Time

In stage three the component must be extracted from the baseplate and support structure used in the additive manufacturing process. In addition to traditional manufacturing tools Wire Electrical Discharge Machine (EDM) is available to remove metals from AM baseplate with a cutting path as small as $21 \mu m$.

In order to achieve the desired material properties the manufactured components must be post-processed. Certain polymers may respond to curing under UV light and the metals may require heat treatment. Two specialised industrial sintering furnaces designed for thermal processing of materials up to 1280 C are

Figure 4: Additive manufacturing process

available as well as UV curing facilities. This process may be necessary to achieve required microstructure and removal residual stresses.

A number of inspection procedures are available in order to verify the dimensional accuracy of the manufactured metamaterials. The influence of manufacturing defects on the meta-behaviour is currently unknown and has not been reported in literature to date. The primary inspection procedures involve high resolution microscopy and CT scanning technology.

The initial DENORMS cell design was created in the open source GMSH software. GMSH can produce a mesh around the designed cell of varying levels of fineness depending on the needs of the design and export the mesh as .stl file. Key quality factors that need to be addressed and inspected at this stage of design are the quality of the feature mesh, the size of the files, any erroneous triangles added in meshing that deviate from the design requirements and any impinged features such as intersecting struts.

Once the design is finalised it can be taken into the 3D builder software as a .stl file. 3D Builder allows the cells to be propagated out in a regular pattern. Its inbuilt repair tools allows designs to be repaired at the joints between cells, remove extraneous triangles formed by the merging of several cells and fill any holes between cells in propagation.

A bottleneck in the production of the geometry relates to the file size and on board memory in the printers. This stage of design is important as the reduction in file size by converting to alternative supported file formats, such as .obj files, reduces the memory requirements by a factor of 5. An even greater reduction is possible by converting to .3mf format but this is not supported by the next stage in the process, namely the proprietary printer software, but might be a potential solution for even larger file sizes required in future.

The simplification tool can also be a strong means to reduce the file size by merging some of the finer features in the design that are not of a resolution available in the manufacturing process. The CAD files are then sliced to form the manufacturing code. Features that are significantly thinner than a single slice will not appear in regular operation but use memory to be stored. The danger in the simplification process is the potential for the simplification to join features across small gaps, thus altering the fundamental design of the cell. The effect of this is that smaller square openings can become rounded or sealed in extreme cases.

As the simplification can also lead to feature removal, a visual inspection of the CAD is conducted using a split tool to provide an internal view of the CAD file. This validation of the features allows errors or issues to be addressed before manufacturing occurs.

This final optimized .obj file can be provided as input to whichever proprietary slicing software is available for the desired printer. There are two main steps in the preparation of a design for print; orientation and support. The design is oriented to reduce overhangs, flat bridging surfaces and other potential causes for build failure such as cups. Overhangs are the most common cause for failure and these are produced by a model which has a long distance before another section or support which can cause the material to sag and no longer join correctly. Cups form in concave features and cause layer separation to occur producing a failed layer in the build which can cascade into total failure.

If at any point a print is not supported from below the laser will solidify the material but it will not be connected to the build. In the Form 2 printer, this cured resin remains in the resin tank and can cause issues during the rest of the build as it can impact other section of the design or become embedded into another feature. Care also has to be taken in the support placement as the support struts can be larger than gaps in the design or the design struts. This can cause issues as the design cannot be extracted intact from the support structure or the design can become compromised with extraneous features.

This problem is most frequently seen at the smaller scales where the support point is placed on the upper bound of a designed hole and completely seals it. A check should be made of support placement and a full visual inspection of the final sliced code should be carried out verifying the required support is present and that no part is filled by a support structure.

Following this the part is ready for manufacture in the printer. There are a few checks that need to be made in order to have a successful print. For example in the Form 2, the baseplate must be clean with no major

gauges or scuffs, these defects will develop over time through regular usage. The resin tank can also develop clouding or have partially cured resin that may interfere with the laser pass. Both of these possible errors are easily corrected but can lead to failed prints if not addressed in a timely manner. The resin tank and resin reservoir must sufficient material for a full print, if the material runs out the print will be paused and potentially cause failure as restarting the print can have poor layer cohesion where the pause occurred.

Following a successful print the part must be removed from the support structure and build plate. The first stage is removing the print from the build plate. The polymer prints include a solid resin base of 2mm attached to the aluminium build plate that keeps the print steady in manufacture however the build plate cannot be put through the material washing system or it will not be able to form a strong bond with subsequent prints. The metal build plates require specialist tools to successfully remove the parts. Once the print is removed from the base plate excess uncured resin or metal powder must be removed. In the resin case this is done using two absolute alcohol baths both for ten minutes. This removes the excess resin but needs to be controlled as alcohol can be absorbed by the resin making it swell and can degrade parts if left for a significant amount of time.

Completed prints undergo a rigorous inspection procedure. The initial inspection is a visual inspection after print removal. This stage of inspection checks for large scale defects such as support failures, missing or damaged cells and layer disconnects. These macro defects usually necessitate a new print or support redesign.

The first quantitative check is to verify that all faces are level. This ensures that the print is not warped or twisted it is possible that uneven curing causes the print to curl inwards on the more cured side, this is due to entrapped and entrained liquid leaving the material and causing a modest amount of shrinkage. To avoid this prints are rotated regularly over the curing period to achieve an even curing.

The next visual inspection is to check all corners are complete and undamaged. As the printing process includes a wiper passing over the print it is possible, at the exposed corners, for a wiper crash to cause damage. The corners are also where any damage in inserting the print into the test apparatus is likely to be noticed as they are the weakest points. This weakness is due to fewer neighbouring cells being available to dissipate force without deforming.

The final element of the visual inspection is to check that all designed channels are formed and clear. The DENORMS cell design has a series of cylindrical channels that air passes through. Any internal defects can usually be seen through these regular channels such as debris being embedded in the material or residue from the support spur failing into the channel. These blockages could potentially impact the effectiveness of the metamaterial.

4 Numerical Modelling

An initial 3D numerical model of the DENORMS cell was developed using a commercial finite element software COMSOL Multiphysics. The proposed DENORMS design was simulated using a fully thermoviscous acoustic model in the COMSOL acoustics module.

The structure of the proposed design as shown in Figure 2 consists of a sphere $r=2.25\text{mm}$ enclosed by a box of sides $a=5\text{mm}$ and three cylinders with $r=1\text{mm}$.

In order to effectively model the losses associated with propagation of sound waves in this problem, the thermal conductivity and viscosity effects which occur in the narrow regions were included. Due to the small size of the unit cell it was appropriate to simulate this problem as a full thermoviscous model. Near the walls, viscous and thermal boundary layers occur, a no-slip condition is applied to the velocity and an isothermal condition for the temperature.

The model in consideration solves for the linearised Navier-Stokes equation,

$$j\omega\rho_0\mathbf{u} = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\mu[\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T]) - \left[\frac{2}{3}\mu - \mu_b\right][\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}]I \quad (1)$$

the conservation equation,

$$j\omega\rho + \rho_0\nabla\mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

and the energy equation in the frequency domain.

$$j\omega\rho_0C_pT = \nabla \cdot (k\nabla T) + j\omega pT_0\alpha_0 \quad (3)$$

where ρ_0 , μ , μ_b , C_p , k and α_0 are the fluids density, dynamic viscosity, bulk viscosity, heat capacity at constant pressure, thermal conductivity and isobaric coefficient of thermal expansion, respectively and ω is the angular frequency. This model requires careful consideration to correctly resolve the acoustic boundary layer. Furthermore, while it is important to accurately capture the thermal and viscous losses by providing refinement towards the boundaries, it is important to keep the number of elements to an acceptable minimum. Far-away from the boundaries the size of the elements can be larger, this will avoid large computation time. The thermoviscous acoustics model is computationally expensive as it solves for the pressure, velocity field and temperature variations.

4.1 Numerical grid

The numerical grid used in the models of different numbers of layers of the DENORMS cell have the same mesh. The appropriate boundary layer thickness required is frequency dependent and can be determined from:

$$\delta = \sqrt{2\nu/\omega} \quad (4)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity of air.

Multiple numerical grids would have to be used for the frequency range of 0-4000 H_z . Due to significantly large computation time required for a fully thermoviscous model for an array of up to ten cells deep, it was decided to have a slightly thicker boundary layer to encapsulate the range of frequencies analysed. As with increasing frequency the boundary layer's thickness should become thinner, the boundary layer thickness was automatically set by COMSOL Multiphysics.

The mesh used for the analyses is shown in 5. A manifold was added to the inlet of the unit cell to capture the entry effects.

4.2 Boundary conditions

A quarter model of the unit cell was used for all models to reduce computation time. Therefore symmetry boundaries were used to model the adjacent cells. A first model with an open ended outlet was used to quantify the velocity entering the cell.

Air properties at $P = 101kP_a$ and $T = 293K$ are used in these analyses.

A harmonic adiabatic pressure condition of amplitude $p = 1P_a$ was set at inlet face of the manifold, and $p = 0P_a$ at the outlet face of the cell. The outer surface of the cells were set as walls. For the other models the outlet surface is closed with $u_t = 0$.

To reduce simulation time a Padé approximation was used in COMSOL so that the response is not calculated at each frequency.

Figure 5: Numerical grid for DENORMS unit cell with inlet manifold

4.3 Results COMSOL

The impedance is calculated at the inlet of the manifold by the following,

$$Z = \frac{P_b}{\bar{u}} \quad (5)$$

Where P_b is the inlet boundary pressure and the average velocity \bar{u} over the surface. The impedance is then translated by the width of the manifold to model the entry into the cell,

$$Z_t = Z_c \left[\frac{Z - Z_c j \tan K_c h}{-Z j \tan K_c h + Z_c} \right] \quad (6)$$

Where Z_c , K_c , h are the characteristic impedance of air, the wave number, and the distance from the inlet of the manifold and cell.

From this, the reflection coefficient R is obtained.

$$R = \frac{Z_t - Z_c}{Z_t + Z_c} \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha = 1 - |R|^2 \quad (8)$$

The velocity and temperature distributions are presented at $f = 1000H_z$ for the unit cell in Figure 6 and Figure 7, and for 4 stacked cells in Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively.

At the time of writing the modelling activity has not been finalised and absorption results as a function of layer depth are not available. The results reported here are outline the modelling approach taken.

Figure 6: Instantaneous local velocity (m/s) unit cell, at $f=1000 H_z$

Figure 7: Total temperature variation(K) unit cell at $f=1000 H_z$

Figure 8: Instantaneous local velocity (m/s) 4 cells, at $f=1000 H_z$

Figure 9: Total temperature variation(K) 4 cells, at $f=1000 H_z$

5 Results

The performance of the acoustic metamaterials is to be assessed against numerical predictions. Modelling work which considers the metamaterial behaviour as simply a surface boundary condition often requires the material behaviour to be expressed in terms of the complex acoustic impedance of the material. Microscale modelling of the interior structure of the material also attempts to predict the complex acoustic impedance of the material. Therefore the primary lab based acoustic validation of the material performance is the measurement of the complex acoustic impedance through impedance tube testing.

The relevant ISO standard for the measurement of the acoustical properties of the material is ISO 10534-2:2001. This standard describes the test rig and procedures for estimating the complex acoustic impedance of a material under normal incidence using the two-microphone or transfer function method. This methodology is used to calculate the reflection and absorption coefficients which are the usual measures used to quantify the performance of an acoustic material.

5.1 Normal Incidence Impedance Tube Testing

Normal incidence impedance tube tests are used to obtain the reflection factor R and absorption coefficient α , in accordance with the international standard ISO 10534-2:2001. In these tests, the sample is placed in an impedance tube as shown in figure 10 (a) which is taken from the ISO standard. The material is backed by a hard, reflective termination. The custom rig used for this work is shown in figure 10 (b).

Figure 10: (a) Impedance tube design ISO 10535-2 (b) TCD Impedance tube rig

In the experimental rig, the hard termination is provided by a 20 mm thick piece of aluminium which can be bolted on the end of the tube. The reflection coefficient is given by the ratio of the reflected wave amplitude (B) to the incident wave amplitude (A) i.e.

$$R = B/A \quad (9)$$

The absorption coefficient α is calculated from the reflection using:

$$\alpha = 1 - |R|^2 \quad (10)$$

Values of the absorption coefficient vary with frequency and range between 0 and 1, with 1 being complete absorption.

The normalised acoustic impedance (Z/ρ_0c) may also be determined from:

$$Z/\rho_0c = (1 + R)/(1 - R) \quad (11)$$

During the test procedure white noise is played through the speaker and the sound pressures p_1 and p_2 are measured by microphones 1 and 2. The complex sound pressures at the two microphones are given by the sum of the forward and backward travelling waves in the tube:

$$p_1 = Ae^{jkx_1} + Be^{-jkx_1} \quad (12)$$

$$p_2 = Ae^{jkx_2} + Be^{-jkx_2} \quad (13)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the distances from the face of the sample to microphone 1 and 2 respectively. These two complex pressures can then be used to find the transfer function H_{12}

$$H_{12} = p_1/p_2 = (Ae^{jkx_1} + Be^{-jkx_1})/(Ae^{jkx_2} + Be^{-jkx_2}) \quad (14)$$

Using $R = B/A$ we get

$$H_{12} = (Ae^{jkx_2} + RAe^{-jkx_2})/(Ae^{jkx_1} + RAe^{-jkx_1}) \quad (15)$$

which can then be rearranged to find the reflection factor:

$$R = (H_{12}e^{jkx_1} - e^{-jkx_2})/(e^{-jkx_2} - H_{12}e^{-jkx_1}) \quad (16)$$

This reflection factor can then be used to calculate the absorption coefficient and acoustic impedance using the above equations.

The reflection and absorption coefficients are affected by factors such as porosity and surface finish of the material, both of which cause viscous energy losses. If the material is compressible, energy can also be lost to internal friction in the material as it is loaded and unloaded by the incident pressure wave. These additional losses will be influenced by the print quality and material used in the manufacture.

5.2 Rig and Sample Design

All the analysis in the previous sections assumed that the waves were all plane waves. Beneath the cut on frequency f_c only plane waves propagate in a duct, higher modes decay exponentially and so when the acoustic signal reaches microphone 1 it is composed of only plane waves. For a tube with circular cross section the cut on frequency is given by

$$f_c = 101/r \quad (17)$$

where r is the radius of the pipe in meters and f_c is in Hertz. For the current rig, the duct diameter is 40 mm and so the cut on is

$$f_c = 101/0.02 = 5050Hz \quad (18)$$

This means we can only perform tests reliably up to a theoretical maximum of 5050 Hz. The lower limit is determined by the speaker and is in the region of 300 Hz. On the left hand side of figure 10 (b) we can see the BMS 4591 speaker which is driven by the output signal of a National Instruments DAQ which has been amplified by a power amplifier. The speaker bolts on to the end of the tube to provide a tight seal with little leakage of sound. The square section on the right of figure 10 (b) is the sample holder which opens to hold cylindrical samples of 40 mm diameter and up to 50 mm thick. The sample holder is held shut by four long bolts with wing nuts.

GRAS 40PH array microphones were chosen to instrument the rig as they have a frequency response of 10 Hz - 20 kHz and upper limit of the dynamic range of 135 dB re 20 μPa allowing for testing up to high pressure amplitudes. The microphones are connected to the National Instruments DAQ and the signals are recorded in Matlab. The microphones are calibrated using the switching methods described in the standards to achieve a calibration transfer function which corrects for any differences in the behaviour of the microphones.

Figure 11 shows the ten layer deep DENORMS cell stacks produced by the three print methods. The high quality polymer prints produced by the Form 2 printer were limited to either single or dual layer disks shown in figure 12. These were then stacked to produce a ten layer sample. The samples were simply manually aligned and held together under their own weight while mounted vertically in the impedance tube. This introduced a potential error as there may have been air gaps between disks and a slight misalignment of the channels, with the alignment error increasing further from the centre of the disk due to any rotation. In contrast the Ultimaker print had a low quality finish and many spurs within the channels. A photo of the print quality compared to the 3D systems sample is shown in figure 13 where these defects are visible. A section of the edge sample which included partially completed cells was chosen as a worst case example of the finish.

Figure 11: 10 cell deep samples: Left - Ultimaker, Centre - Form 2, Right - 3d Systems

Figure 12: Form 2 single and dual layer disks

6 Experimental Results

The results for the ten layer deep prints from the three printers are shown in figure 14. From all three prints there is a double peak in the absorptivity in the regions of 1000 Hz and 3500 Hz. There is excellent agreement between the 3D systems sample and the Form 2 sample for the location and amplitude of the first peak while there is some divergence on the frequency of the second peak. The Ultimaker sample produces both peaks at lower frequencies and high amplitudes. The increase in absorptivity can likely be attributed to the remaining spurs and low quality surface finish of the sample introducing additional losses within the

Figure 13: Comparison of print quality between the 3D systems (left) and Ultimaker (right) prints

channels. It appears from these results that any errors associated with the manual positioning of the polymer disks are of less importance than the quality of the interior geometry and from this we can conclude that the Form 2 may be a viable, low cost system suitable for producing sample for comparison to numerical models. The divergence of the Ultimaker samples from the 3D systems sample is likely too great to allow it to be used for validation purposes.

Figure 14: Absorption coefficient for three different prints of the 10 layer deep DENORMS cell

Due to the necessity to limit manufacture to single and dual layer disks on the Form 2 it was also possible to test other combinations of disks to produce different numbers of layers. Figure 15 reports the experimental results for five to ten layers deep. A clear trend can be seen in the location and magnitude of the peaks. As the number of layers decreases the location of both peaks shift to higher frequencies and the magnitude of the absorptivity drops.

Figure 15: Absorption coefficient for 5-10 layers deep of the DENORMS cell printed on the Form 2

7 Conclusion

This work has reported on the design of a periodic acoustic metamaterial that is suitable for use as a benchmark validation case. The design was realised through three different additive manufacturing technologies which ranged from low cost desktop printers to state of the art machines. Experimental testing demonstrated good agreement between the Form 2 mid range printer and the state of the art 3D systems machine. This indicated that manufacture of a benchmark validation material may be possible at relatively low cost using current technologies. The use of a Ultimaker printer highlighted the potential for low quality prints to significantly influence the achieved performance, this is considered an obstacle for the production of validation data using this type of printer technology.

Clear trends as a function of depth were identified in the experimental results which were also achieved using a simple mounting procedure of the disks of high resolution low cost samples from the Form 2. The DENORMS design is therefore highly suitable for use as a benchmark and validation tool.

Initial modelling of the material was attempted in the COMSOL commercial tool set. At the time of writing this modelling was not complete and no comparison to the experimental results has been attempted. Further work will improve on the numerical results and attempt to match the experimental data.

The current scale of the design is at the limit of the low cost additive manufacturing technologies but finer scales can readily be achieved in the state of the art machines. Additional test samples at smaller scales are also planned to provide further data for model validation where parameters such as cell size, sphere size and cylinder size.

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References

- [1] Min Yang, Shuyu Chen, Caixing Fu, and Ping Sheng. Optimal sound-absorbing structures. *Materials Horizons*, 4(4):673–680, July 2017.
- [2] Yifan Zhu, Xudong Fan, Bin Liang, Jianchun Cheng, and Yun Jing. Ultrathin Acoustic Metasurface-Based Schroeder Diffuser. *Physical Review X*, 7(2):021034, June 2017.
- [3] Reza Ghaffarivardavagh, Jacob Nikolajczyk, R. Glynn Holt, Stephan Anderson, and Xin Zhang. Horn-like space-coiling metamaterials toward simultaneous phase and amplitude modulation. *Nature Communications*, 9(1):1349, April 2018.
- [4] Changru Chen, Zhibo Du, Gengkai Hu, and Jun Yang. A low-frequency sound absorbing material with subwavelength thickness. *Applied Physics Letters*, 110(22):221903, May 2017.
- [5] Yangbo Xie, Bogdan-Ioan Popa, Lucian Zigoneanu, and Steven A. Cummer. Measurement of a Broadband Negative Index with Space-Coiling Acoustic Metamaterials. *Physical Review Letters*, 110(17):175501, April 2013.